

Hypervalent iodine(III) mediated synthesis of 2-substituted benzoxazoles[†]

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Manuscript received 3 September 2003

2-Substituted benzoxazoles (6a-j, 7a-e, 7j-l) have been synthesized via the oxidative intramolecular cyclization of Schiff's bases (4a-j, 5a-e, 5j-l) using iodobenzene diacetate (IBD) as an oxidant in dry methanol. A one-pot procedure for the synthesis of 6a-j, 7a-e and 7j-l starting from *o*-aminophenol/*p*-chloro-*o*-aminophenol and aldehydes has also been developed.

An explosive growth in the field of use of organohypervalent iodine in organic synthesis has been witnessed over the last few decades¹⁻³. In particular, organoiodine(III) reagents such as iodobenzene diacetate (IBD), iodobenzene bis(trifluoro)acetate (IBTA) and [hydroxy(tosyloxy)iodo]benzene (HTIB) have shown wide application in the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds². Recent work from our laboratory has emphasized the increasing utility of IBD and HTIB in the area of heterocyclic compounds³. As part of these investigations, we have earlier reported that oxidation of phenolic Schiff's bases (SBs) with IBD in acetonitrile or methanol leads to a facile intramolecular cyclization providing the synthesis of 2-arylbenzoxazoles⁴.

In view of the great biological and analytical importance of 2-substituted benzoxazoles⁵ and realizing that low toxicity, easy handling and simple experimentation involved in organoiodine(III) based methods have made this area more attractive, it was worthwhile to extend the reaction to the general synthesis of 2-substituted benzoxazoles.

Our preliminary report dealt with the oxidation of SBs derived from *o*-aminophenol and *p*-substituted benzaldehydes⁴ containing simple substituents. Since then, we have examined the oxidation of a large number of SBs to study the scope of I(III)-mediated approach for the synthesis of various 2-substituted benzoxazoles. In addition, one-pot procedure involving oxidation of *in situ* generated Schiff's bases has also been developed. We wish to report herein a fuller account of the results on I(III)-mediated synthesis of 2-substituted benzoxazoles.

Results and discussion

The results of the oxidation of SBs (4a-e) obtained from *o*-aminophenol (1) and *p*-substituted benzaldehydes (3a-e) have shown that oxidative cyclization occurs smoothly. Schiff's bases obtained from *p*-chloro-*o*-aminophenol (2) and *p*-substituted benzaldehydes (3a-e, I) also underwent smooth oxidative cyclization.

To investigate the effect on phenolic hydroxy group, the 4f obtained from *o*-aminophenol (1) and salicylaldehyde (3f) was treated with 1.1 equivalent of IBD in methanol. The reaction afforded 2-(2-hydroxyphenyl)benzoxazole (6f) in 64% yield. The result clearly shows that oxidative intramolecular cyclization is preferred over oxidation of phenolic hydroxy group. When 5k, synthesized from *p*-chloro-*o*-aminophenol (2) and vanillin (3k), was oxidised with IBD in methanol, the reaction afforded the expected product 2-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)-5-chlorobenzoxazole (7k) but yield was poor (40%), attempts to isolate any other products were unsuccessful.

In view of the ability of I(III) reagent such as IBD to attack double bond, 4j, obtained from 1 and cinnamaldehyde (3j), was treated with 1.1 equivalent of IBD in methanol. Since the reaction afforded 2-styrylbenzoxazole (6j) in 48% yield, it appears that the major route in this reaction is oxidative cyclization of 4j. The same procedure successfully converted 5j, available from 2 and cinnamaldehyde, to 2-styryl-5-chlorobenzoxazole (7j) in 40% yield. Further, the newly developed method was found to be suitable for the synthesis of 2-heteroarylbenzoxazoles, namely, 2-(2-furyl)-

[†]Dedicated to Professor S. M. Mukherji for his contributions to this Department.

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benzoxazole (**6g**), 2-thienylbenzoxazole (**6h**), 2-(5-benzoxazolyl)thienylbenzoxazole (**6i**). The results clearly show that heteroaryl moiety is not affected under the oxidative conditions (Table 1).

Scheme 1

It is relevant to mention in connection with the present study that hypervalent iodine oxidation of SBs is known to give different products depending upon the nature of SBs. For example, **8**, derived from aldehydes and anilines, on treatment with IBD undergo, oxidative rearrangement with the formation of azo compounds (**11**) and aldehydes (**12**) via the dimerisation of nitrene intermediates (**9**) and hydrolysis of acetals (**10**) respectively (Scheme 2)⁶.

Scheme 2

Since no such rearranged products were isolated in the hypervalent iodine oxidation of SBs investigated in the present investigation, it is obvious that the presence of *o*-hydroxy group in SBs changes the course of reaction outlined in Scheme 2. Thus, formation of the benzoxazoles may be explained by a different route. A plausible mechanism for the conversion of SB to benzoxazole can be outlined as follows :

Nitrogen (-N=CH-) of the SB being more nucleophilic than intramolecularly bonded *o*-hydroxy group, probably attacks at the iodine of IBD with simultaneous intramolecular participation of *o*-hydroxy group to compensate the elec-

Scheme 3

tron density on methine group thereby forming the adduct **13**. Finally, **13** aromatizes with the elimination of iodobenzene and acetic acid to afford 2-substituted benzoxazoles (Scheme 3).

Scheme 4

One-pot procedure :

The most significant feature of the present study is the development of one-pot procedure for the synthesis of 2-substituted benzoxazoles. Thus, *o*-aminophenol (**1**) was heated under reflux with *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde (**3d**) in methanol for five minutes. Subsequently the reaction mixture was treated with 1.1 equivalent of IBD. Usual workup and purification afforded the desired product 2-(4-nitrophenyl)-benzoxazole (**6d**) in 76% yield. One-pot procedure was successfully applied to the synthesis of other 2-substituted benzoxazoles and the yields were either comparable or better than those from two steps procedure (Table 1).

Table 1. Physical data of 2-substituted benzoxazoles

Compd. no.	X Ar	M.p. °C	Lit m.p. °C	Yield ^{a,b} %
6a	H C ₆ H ₅	101	102 ⁴	83 (67)
6b	H 4-ClC ₆ H ₄	147	147 ⁴	87 (70)
6c	H 4-OMeC ₆ H ₄	100	101 ⁴	82 (64)
6d	H 4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	266–68	266–68 ⁴	93 (76)
6e	H 4-MeC ₆ H ₄	112	113–14 ⁴	87 (68)
6f	H 2-OHC ₆ H ₄	207	206 ^{10a}	64 (50)
6g	H 2-furyl	81–82	82–84 ^{10b}	68 (60)
6h	H 2-thienyl	105–106	107 ^{10c}	64 (52)
6i	H 2-(5-benzoxazolyl)thienyl	217–18	217–20 ^{10d}	75 (64)
6j	H CH=CHC ₆ H ₅	79	81 ^{10c}	48
7a	Cl C ₆ H ₅	102	101–02 ^{10c}	67 (60)

Table-1 (contd.)

7b	Cl 4-ClC ₆ H ₄	186	190 ^{10f}	71
7c	Cl 4-OMeC ₆ H ₄	146	148 ^{10f}	61
7d	Cl 4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	238–39	240 ^{10f}	72
7e	Cl 4-MeC ₆ H ₄	137	138 ^{10g}	60
7j	Cl CH=CHC ₆ H ₅	104	<i>c</i>	45
7k	Cl 3-OMe-4-OHC ₆ H ₃	186	<i>c</i>	40
7l	Cl 4-FC ₆ H ₄	142	<i>c</i>	68 (60)

^aYields of the isolated pure products w.r.t. the quantity of Schiff's base.

^bYields (in parenthesis) of the pure products w.r.t. the quantity of *o*-aminophenol/*p*-chloro-*o*-aminophenol by using one-pot procedure.

^cThese are new products and their structures were confirmed by their spectral (IR, ¹H NMR) and elemental analysis (C, H, N).

Effect of solvents :

To study the effect of solvent on the yield of 2-substituted benzoxazoles, we treated **5b**, obtained from **2** and **3b**, with 1.1 equivalents of IBD in different solvents (methanol, acetonitrile and chloroform). The reaction proceeded with equal efficiency in all the solvents and yields were comparable.

Conclusion :

The significance and limitations of this iodine(III) mediated approach can be summarised as under : (i) A convenient synthesis of 2-substituted benzoxazoles is available. The method is quite general and has advantages over reported methods which include toxic and unsafe reagents such as lead tetraacetate⁷, nickel peroxide⁸, copper(I) chloride in the presence of dioxygen⁹. (ii) The reaction conditions are mild and compatible with the presence of other oxidizable groups such as phenolic hydroxyl group and double bond, although the yields in the case of *p*-hydroxyphenyl derivatives are relatively low. (iii) It offers a one-pot synthesis of 2-substituted benzoxazoles with very convenient experimental procedure. (iv) Nitrogen and sulphur of heteroaryl moieties are not affected under the reaction conditions.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. SBs were prepared according to literature procedure. SBs and 2-substituted benzoxazoles were identified by their comparison of literature melting points and spectral data. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ at 300 MHz.

Schiff bases : In general, the SBs were prepared by refluxing 0.1 mol of *o*-aminophenol/*p*-chloro-*o*-aminophenol and 0.15 mol of aldehyde in 100 ml ethanol. The SBs precipitated on cooling the mixture and were recrystallised from ethanol.

Synthesis of 2-substituted benzoxazoles from SBs : General procedure :

To a solution of Schiff's base (10 mmol) in 10 ml dry methanol, was added IBD (10.10 mmol) and the mixture was stirred for five to ten minutes. Solvent was evaporated in vacuo to bring the volume to one third. Crystalline solids (**6b**, **d**, **f**, **i**), (**7b**, **d**, **f**) separated out on keeping the reaction mixture at room temperature for 4–6 h. Solids, thus obtained, were filtered and washed with methanol. Alternatively, crude product (**6a**, **c**, **e**, **g**, **h**, **j**) (**7a**, **c**, **e**, **j**, **k**, **l**) was purified by column chromatograph on silica gel (60–120 mesh) with petroleum ether and ethyl acetate (10 : 1) mixture as eluent to afford the title products. Their physical data are listed in Table 1.

One-pot synthesis of 2-substituted benzoxazoles from *o*-aminophenol : General procedure :

To the solution of *o*-aminophenol (**6**)/*p*-chloro-*o*-aminophenol (**7**) (10 mmol) in methanol was added aryl/heteroaryl aldehyde (15 mmol). The reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 2–3 h till the completion of the reaction (monitored by tlc). The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and IBD (10.10 mmol) was added and stirred for 5–10 min. Method of isolation and purification was same as in stepwise procedure.

Acknowledgement

The work reported in this paper has been supported through DRDO (India) Extramural Basic Research Grant No. ERIP/ER/0103294/M/01 and is subject to sponsor's disclaimer.

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